

Leaf Prints

Early Cameraless Photography and Botany

Katharina Steidl Histories of photography generally let their story begin by pointing out the ancestors of the art. These include experiments on the blackening effect of light on silver salts in the 18th century, as well as the drawing aid known as the “camera obscura”; a darkened room or portable box with a little hole in it capable of producing an upside-down image of the outside scenery. The combination of these led to what is now commonly understood as photography: the creation of a camera-made image. This definition ignores the importance of those photographs made without a camera, which were not only produced at the beginning of – or even before – photography but throughout the entire 19th century.

Cameraless images, or photograms as they are called today, were fundamental for the conceptualization of photography. Through an examination of images made without a camera, William Henry Fox Talbot, the English inventor of photography, was not only able to develop certain ideas concerning an automatic, self-generated image through direct observation, but also to evolve a concept of objectivity based on the constitutive moment of the contact between the object and photosensitive surface. To a large extent, this was the result of his interest in botany and established illustration techniques in the botanical field. An analysis of Talbot’s early photograms of plants opens up discussions about how to visualize botanical compendia, as well as the extent to which the connection between botany and gender influenced the perception of the photogram. From the beginning, there were strong links between photography with or without a camera and concepts of visibility and invisibility. This not only meant the visualization or transformation of something invisible or not visible to the human eye into a visible pictorial representation; it also says something about how vision, perception and the photographic image were amalgamated leading to certain stylistic preferences or compositions in photography. Furthermore, it can be said that depictions in cameraless and camera photography are based on adopted representational models that differ from each other to a great extent.

Pictures of flowers and leaves

Shortly after the French announcement of photography, William Henry Fox Talbot presented his photographic invention at a meeting held at the Royal Institution on January 25, 1839. On this occasion, Talbot introduced his method of paper photography named “photogenic drawing”. This term encompassed both photographs taken with a camera and photograms. To produce such photographs without a camera, he arranged flat objects such as lace patterns and leaves of plants directly on a photosensitive surface and exposed them to the rays of the sun (fig. 1).

Michael Faraday announced the new discovery to the more than 300 people attending the lecture on that evening with the following words: “No human hand has hith-

Figure 1
 William Henry Fox Talbot, *Botanical Specimen*,
 photogenic drawing negative,
 c. 1835, 22,4 x 18,3 cm.
 National Media Museum Bradford.

erto traced such lines as these drawings display: And what man may hereafter do, now that Dame Nature has become his drawing mistress, it is impossible to predict.”¹ With these lines, Faraday made associations between two media: photography and drawing. But most of all, he pointed towards a gendered form of drawing, as nature was thought to be feminine and drawing in those days was a popular female pastime.² After this, the audience was able to examine examples of Talbot’s photogenic drawings on the walls of the upper library.³ There were camera-obscura pictures among the exhibits but contact prints of plants, flowers, leaves and laces that Talbot had possibly produced in the years 1835 to 1838 were more numerous. On February 2, a letter from Talbot to the editor of *The Literary Gazette* was published in which he commented on this presentation. Although he emphasized that he could only show “what I happened to have with me in town”, he managed to present the audience a variety of photograms, copies from engravings and camera photographs:

1. Anonym, ‘Royal Institution’, in: *The Literary Gazette and Journal of the Belles Lettres, Arts, Sciences, &c.*, no. 1150, 2 February 1839, 74–75.

2. See Ann Bermingham, *Learning to Draw. Studies in the Cultural History of a Polite and Useful Art*, New Haven: Yale University Press 2000; Carol Armstrong, ‘Cameraless: From Natural Illustrations and Nature Prints to Manual and Photogenic Drawings and Other Botanographs’,

in: *Ibid.* and Catherine de Zegher (eds.), *Ocean Flowers. Impressions from Nature*, exhibition catalogue, New York 2004, 87–165.

3. See Mike Weaver (ed.), *Henry Fox Talbot. Selected Texts and Bibliography*, Oxford: Clip Press 1992, 45f.

*Among them were pictures of flowers and leaves; a pattern of lace; figures taken from painted glass; a view of Venice copied from an engraving; some images formed by the Solar Microscope, viz. a slice of wood very highly magnified, exhibiting the pores of two kinds, one set much smaller than the other, and more numerous. Another Microscopic sketch, exhibiting the reticulations on the wing of an insect. Finally: various pictures, representing the architecture of my house in the country; all these made with the Camera Obscura in the summer of 1835.*⁴

Stressing that “the most remarkable of these, is undoubtedly the copying of a distant object,” he nevertheless insisted on the fact that, “one perhaps more calculated for universal use is the power of depicting exact facsimiles of smaller objects which are in the vicinity of the operator, such as flowers, leaves, engravings, &c., which may be accomplished with great facility, and often with a degree of rapidity that is almost marvellous.”⁵ Even though he stated that camera photography made it possible to obtain images or copies of the outer world, Talbot diagnosed a universal or general use in the contact printing process of the photogram. It could therefore be argued that he saw much greater potential in his cameraless technique of copying botanical specimen, laces or engravings. Besides, in this context, the term “facsimile” allows a definition of the photogram as an exact representation or 1:1 copy of the original leaf created through contact.

In his first account on photography, which was read to the Royal Society on 31 January 1839 and published privately, he made a strong connection between photography and botany. Entitled *Some account of the art of photogenic drawing, or, the process by which natural objects may be made to delineate themselves without the aid of the artist's pencil*, he described his first experiences with contact prints of flowers and leaves, either fresh or dried from his herbarium.⁶ With this printing process, which he called a “natural process”, he “expected that a kind of image or picture would be produced, resembling to a certain degree the object from which it was derived.”⁷ This resemblance between the image and object – which Talbot hoped to be almost, but not totally, identical – needs to be understood as a visualization through transformation. In the case of his photogenic drawings of plants and leaves, he declared that these objects were depicted “with the utmost truth and fidelity, exhibiting even the venation of the leaves, the minute hairs that clothe the plant, &c.”⁸ In this point, it could be said that, for Talbot, photograms could resemble the original to a certain degree, in so far as cameraless photographs are able to highlight or uncover certain qualities of the object and, at the same time, reveal other structures only schematically. Photogenic drawings of botanical specimens, in particular, accentuate the nearly invisible structures of venation and trichome with great accuracy. Depending on their transparency, this method could also result in an image predominantly

4. William Henry Fox Talbot, 'Photogenic Drawing: To the Editor of the Literary Gazette', in: *The Literary Gazette and Journal of the Belles Lettres, Arts, Sciences, &c.*, No. 1150, 2 February 1839, 73–74.

5. Talbot 1839 (reference 4), 73.

6. William Henry Fox Talbot, 'Some Account of the Art of Photogenic Drawing, or, the Process by Which Natural Objects May be Made to Delineate Themselves without the Aid of the Artist's Pencil', reprint in: Beaumont Newhall (ed.), *Photography: Essays and Images*, New York: Museum of Modern Art 1980, 23–31.

7. Talbot 1980 (reference 6), 23.

8. Talbot 1980 (reference 6), 24.

Figure 2
 'Bryonia Alba', Plate 260 from David Heinrich
 Hoppe and Johann Mayr, *Ectypa Plantarum
 Ratisbonensium, oder Abdrücke derjenigen
 Pflanzen, welche um Regensburg wild wachsen,
 Erstes Hundert, Regensburg 1787.*

gravings or paintings made by an artist, nature printing was an inexpensive alternative for illustration in botany. The leading argument for this technique was that plants could be copied without any interference on the part of the scientist or artist to provide an unsophisticated conception of nature. In particular, the visual effect of an impression evokes a special kind of presence in the image totally different from other forms of reproduction. A mechanical method like nature printing could realize the ideal of the unmediated access to nature revealing an image which was considered true to nature. Complex structures like the venation and trichome of a plant were easily and precisely reproduced. In terms of time, this method coincides with the popularization of science. Not only scientists, naturalists and apothecaries ordered such books, amateurs and interested lay people were also among the subscribers.⁹

defined by its outlines or nuances of shading between light and dark.

He mentions that his contact printing process would be particularly useful for naturalists travelling to distant countries as they would not need to draw the plants they discovered but could simply make a photogenic drawing of them.

Photogenic drawings and nature printing

To create cameraless photographs, the object to be photographed and the surface of the paper need to be in direct contact with each other, producing an image of the botanical specimen in light and shadow. The translucent parts of the object would result in a darker impression; more transparent parts would produce a lighter coloration. This method of placing a plant in direct contact with a surface to make an impression was a common technique in botany known as "nature printing". Mainly used in 18th-century Germany, and to some extent also in Britain, printing from nature at the time meant covering a plant with black ink and pressing it onto a piece of paper, which subsequently left a black impression mostly defined by its outline (fig. 2). Delicate storage formats in botany such as herbaria, in which plant specimens were collected, could therefore be replaced and easily be exchanged. Compared to en-

9. See Kerrin Klinger, 'Ectypa Plantarum und Dilettantismus um 1800. Zur Naturtreue botanischer Pflanzenselbstdrucke', in: Olaf Breidbach (ed.), *Natur im Kasten*, exhibition catalogue, Jena 2010, 80–96.

It is very likely that Talbot was aware of this printing technique as he and his family had a lifelong interest in botany.¹⁰ As a schoolboy, he and a friend compiled an inventory entitled *Plants Indigenous to Harrow: Flora Harroviensis* in 1814–1815. In 1826, he made an expedition to the Ionian Islands and Corfu where he identified several new plants. Furthermore, he corresponded with leading botanists, discussing and classifying plants he had recently discovered and, in this way, steadily increased his knowledge of botany. Among his correspondents were William Jackson Hooker, Antonio Bertoloni and John Lindley. His election as a fellow of the Linnean Society in 1829 is an indication that he was one of the most notable botanists of the period. At Lacock Abbey, his home after 1827, Talbot arranged a botanical garden and collected specimens for his herbarium, later using them for his botanical photogenic drawings. In this garden, which was restored by the National Trust in 1999, he also added a conservatory

for exotic and delicate plants. The seeds and bulbs for the garden were exchanged with professional botanists, collected during botanical trips or purchased from nurseries.¹¹ In a letter to John Herschel he emphasizes his interest as follows: “Botany is a science to which I am particularly attracted and have paid much attention during my travels through many parts of Europe.”¹²

The photogram as botanical illustration

The photogram as an illustration technique in botany was a major objective for Talbot. Shortly after the announcement of paper photography, he tried to realize a botanical publication with photogenic drawings of plants in collaboration with leading botanists of his time. To promote his idea of a botanical oeuvre with cameraless images, he corresponded with the Italian botanist Antonio Bertoloni sending him a total of thirty-six photogenic drawings.¹³ Despite Talbot’s efforts to perform a joint botany project, Bertoloni did not seem convinced as this undertaking was never fulfilled.

In March 1839, he also sent cameraless photographs to William Hooker, a well-known botanist of his time, suggesting they undertake a joint project on British or foreign plants. But Hooker expressed his doubts, mentioning that plants should be represented “either by outline or with the shadows of the flower (which of course express shape) distinctly marked.” He continues: “Your beautiful *Campanula hederacea* was very pretty as to general

Figure 5
William Henry Fox Talbot, *Leaf*, photogenic drawing negative, c. 1840, 8,9 x 8,6 cm. National Media Museum Bradford.

10. See Russel Roberts, ‘The Order of Nature’, in: Catherine Coleman (ed.), *Huellas de la Luz. El Arte y los Experimentos de William Henry Fox Talbot*, exhibition catalogue, Madrid 2001, 367–368; H. J. P. Arnold, *William Henry Fox Talbot. Pioneer of Photography and Man of Science*, London: Hutchinson 1977, 34–35, 254–266.

11. See Katie Fretwell, ‘Fox Talbot’s Botanic Garden’, in: *Apollo*, vol. 159, no. 506, 2004, 25–28.

12. William Henry Fox Talbot to John Herschel, 9 March 1833, HS 17:269, Royal Society Archives, London. For the correspondence of Talbot see <<http://foxtalbot.dmu.ac.uk>> [27.01.2011]

13. See Graham Smith, ‘Talbot and Botany. The Bertoloni Album’, in: *History of Photography*, vol. 17, no. 1, 1993, 33–48; Malcolm Daniel, ‘L’Album Bertoloni’, in: Giuseppina Benassati and Andrea Emiliani (eds.), *Fotografia & Fotografi a Bologna, 1839-1900*, exhibition catalogue, Bologna 1992, 73–78. Bertoloni collected Talbot’s photogenic drawings in an album entitled *Album di Disegni Fotogenici*, which is now held at the Metropolitan Museum in New York.

Figure 6
William Henry Fox Talbot, *Astrantia Major*, 13
November 1838, Photogenic Drawing Negative,
17,3 x 9,5 cm. National Media Museum
Bradford.

Figure 7
'*Astrantia Major*', Plate 749, from Albert
Gottfried Dietrich, *Flora Regni Borussici: Flora
des Königreichs Preussen oder Abbildung und
Beschreibung der in Preussen wiederwachsenden
Pflanzen*, vol. 11, Berlin 1843.

effect – but it did not express the swelling of the flower, nor the calyx, nor the veins of the leaves distinctly.”¹⁴ In fact, a lot of cameraless pictures made by Talbot were able to visualize the venation of the leaves of a plant, which otherwise would not easily be recognized through direct or unmediated observation as seen in figure 5. Depending on the thickness of the plant, quite often only the outlines are represented in the photogenic drawings giving no distinct internal details of the object. Comparing one of Talbot’s photogenic drawings of *Astrantia Major*, made in November 1838 at the same time as the pictures he sent to Hooker, and a botanical illustration of the same plant published in 1843 by the German botanist Albert Gottfried Dietrich in his *Flora Regni Borussici*, clarifies what a botanical illustration around 1840 needed to reveal (figs. 6 and 7).¹⁵ Talbot’s photogenic drawing depicts a single plant in light brown on a brownish background. Mainly delineated by its outline and marginal internal details, this depiction of an umbellifer would result in an ambiguous identification in botany. In contrast, the coloured lithograph represents not a single, but a typical plant and depicts all the essential, and therefore characteristic, parts necessary for identifying the species. In addition to the delineation of the roots, the inflorescence and the seeds in outline drawing, the plant itself is given in its natural colours. The major part of the picture is dominated by the sprout that, due to its height of about 30–100 cm, is cut into two parts: a lower segment with the beginning of the roots and an upper segment with flowers and seeds. While the photogram can only reproduce a single plant in 1:1, an illustration allows the artist to represent

14. Arnold 1977 [reference 10], 265.

15. Albert Gottfried Dietrich, *Flora Regni Borussici. Flora des Königreichs Preussen oder Abbildung und Beschreibung der in Preussen wildwachsenden Pflanzen*, vol. 11, Berlin: Oehmigte 1843.

Figure 9
*The Mirror of Literature,
 Amusement and Instruction,*
 cover of 20 April 1839,
 printed by J. Limbird.

specimens in reduced or augmented size and accentuate the characteristic parts of a typical plant. As monochromatic pictures, the only claim of being true to nature that photograms have, results from the constitutive element of the contact. Therefore, efforts to include photogenic drawings in botany rely to a great extent on models such as nature printing and the mechanical impression of a plant on paper, affirming its truth through contact.

When dealing with its formal appearance, it could also be argued that photography without a camera relies on ancestors like silhouettes, cut-outs and outline-drawings that had been popular since the mid-18th century when discussions about the contour as “linear abstraction” arose.¹⁶ Leaving aside linear perspective and spatial illusionism, both in artistic as well as in scientific illustration, a tendency towards stylization through a concentration on outline drawing was prominent.¹⁷ This contour line made it possible to visualize those elements of the form which were considered “characteristic”.

In 18th-century publications using nature-printing techniques, the black contour line of a single plant produced by this process sometimes seemed to be insufficient as quite a lot of illustrations were manipulated by overpainting in opaque colours and sometimes even flowers, fruits etc. were added.¹⁸

Photogenic drawings in journals

To promote and introduce their readers to Talbot’s invention of photography, journals including the low-price weekly *The Mirror of Literature, Amusement and Instruction* published several articles explaining the formal and chemical characteristics of photogenic drawings (fig. 9). On 20 April 1839, this magazine printed the first reproduction of a photogenic drawing of three ferns with white parts illustrating the possibilities and impossibilities of this medium to visualize opacity, transparency and translucence. This *Fac-simile of a Photogenic Drawing* was made in woodcut after a photogram by Golding Bird, “a distinguished botanist”, who followed Talbot’s newly invented process.¹⁹ Coloured in brownish-red tint to match that of the original, the title page caused great excitement and interest among its readers. In the subsequent issue, it was noted that:

16. Robert Rosenblum, *The International Style of 1800. A Study in Linear Abstraction*, reprint, New York: Garland 1976.

17. See Werner Busch, ‘Umrißzeichnungen und Arabeske als Kunstprinzipien des 19. Jahrhunderts’, in: Regine Timm (ed.), *Buchillustration im 19. Jahrhundert*, Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz 1988, 117–148; Claudia Blümle and Armin Schäfer, ‘Organismus und Kunstwerk. Zur Einführung’, in: *Ibid* (ed.), *Struktur, Figur, Kontur. Abstraktion in Kunst und Lebenswissenschaften*, Zürich: Diaphanes 2007, 9–25.

18. Peter Heilmann argues that Kniphof printed each plant six times, three times on each side. In doing so, the first dark copy and the last light one were coloured, whereas the second one was left in its original condition.

See Peter Heilmann, ‘Über den Naturselbstdruck und seine Anwendung’, in: Silke Opitz (ed.), *Die Sache selbst*, exhibition catalogue, Weimar 2002, 100–109, 103.

19. Anonymous, ‘A Treatise on Photogenic Drawing’, in: *The Mirror of Literature, Amusement and Instruction*, 20 April 1839, 243–244, 243. This article is a partial reprint of: Golding Bird, ‘Observations on the Application of Heliographic or Photogenic Drawing to Botanical Purposes; with an Account of an Economic Mode of Preparing the Paper’, in: *The Magazine of Natural History*, vol. 3, New Series, April 1839, 188–192.

Figure 10
The Magazine of Science and School of Arts,
 cover of 27 April 1839,
 printed by G. Francis.

The fac-simile of the photogenic drawing in our last number has produced a much greater sensation than we had anticipated; but still we are not surprised at this excitement, for the engraving gave a most accurate idea of the photogenic picture, which represents the fern with such extreme fidelity that not only its veins, but the imperfections, and accidental folding of the leaves of the specimen are copied, - the greater opacity on the folded parts being represented by the large white patches on our fac-simile.²⁰

According to this remark, the photogenic drawings were not so much praised for the exact identification of the plant as for the precise representation of the ferns discernible by their minute details and imperfections. In the reprint of an article accompanying and explicating the cover illustration, Bird compares the French and the English photogenic processes declaring his preference for the latter. Dr. Bird identifies the major application of the photogenic drawing process for botanical purposes, as the botanist might “procure beautiful outline drawings of many plants, with a degree of accuracy which, otherwise, he could not hope to obtain.”²¹

One could not only visualize “every scale, nay, every projecting hair,” but also the venation and “the character and habit of the plant.”²² But not all plants seem to be appropriate for the photogenic drawing process: “Among those classes of plants which appear to be more fitted than others for representation by this process, may be ranked the ferns, grasses, and umbelliferous plants.”²³

In the ex-post preface accompanying volume thirty-three in 1839, the editor of *The Mirror* states a “present thirst for Botanical knowledge”, which he recognizes most of all in “the instruction of the female sex.” He continues by emphasizing the journal’s reports on photogenic drawing calling it an “accomplishment” and “very pleasing and astonishing art.”²⁴ This analogization of botany, female accomplishments and the simple and abstracting technique of the photogram gets more explicit in another magazine devoted to rational and scientific amusement, as well as to processes employed in the fine and ornamental arts.

On 27 April 1839, the front cover of “The Magazine of Science and School of Arts” presented three schematic woodcuts after photogenic drawings of a lace pattern and flowers as seen in figure 10.²⁵ Among the objects generating the best effect in cameraless photography, the accompanying report mentions “lace, especially black lace – printed and checked muslin – feathers – dried plants, particularly the ferns, the sea-weeds, and the light grasses ...”²⁶ After a description of photographs made with a camera obscura and those made without a camera, the article concludes:

20. Anonymous, ‘The New Art – Photography’, in: *The Mirror of Literature, Amusement and Instruction*, 27 April 1839, 262–263, 262.

21. Anonymous 1839 [reference 18], 243.

22. Anonymous 1839 [reference 18], 244.

23. Anonymous 1839 [reference 18], 244.

24. Editor, ‘Preface’, in: *The Mirror of Literature, Amusement and Instruction*, vol. 33, 1839, n.p.

25. To be more precise, the woodcuts were obtained by directly exposing the objects on wood made light sensitive. See G. Francis, ‘Important Application of Photogenic Drawing’, in: *The Magazine of Science and School of Arts*, 27 April 1839, 28.

26. Anonymous, ‘Photogenic Drawing’, in: *The Magazine of Science and School of Arts*, 27 April 1839, 26–28, 28.

Figure 11
 Anna Atkins, 'Alaria esculenta',
 from *Photographs of British Algae*,
 Part XII, 1849/1850.
 Kelvingrove Art Gallery and Museum.

albums.²⁸ The illustration process of photogenic drawing seemed appropriate for women involved in natural history and allowed them scientific and artistic expression.

In the first reviews, instruction manuals and handbooks of photography, the process of photogenic drawing without a camera and its repeated description to impress objects such as lace patterns, leaves and plants was frequently put in the context of botany, feminine recreation or amusement and not regarded as being suitable for scientific purposes. To return to the beginning of my article, a possible answer to the question of why photograms from the 19th century have generally not found a place in the history of photography could lead us to the feminization of this medium and its consecutive classification as items not worth collecting. As a consequence of the research undertaken by Larry Schaaf and Carol Armstrong, Anna Atkins is now included among the renowned cameraless photographers working with John Herschel's cyanotype (blueprinting) process (fig. 11).²⁹ Nevertheless there are a number of less

*We have hitherto considered this art as applicable only to the delineation of flat and trivial objects, and as rather conducive to amusement than utility; but as paper acts not only by direct but reflected light, it may be made subservient to much more important uses, by the assistance of such lenses and mirrors as reflect the images given to natural objects upon a screen or medium. The chief instruments of this character are the camera obscura and the solar microscope.*²⁷

According to this conclusion, the photogenic drawing process of flat objects was regarded as being inferior to camera photography and merely a pastime method to reproduce "trivial" objects.

Women and photogenic drawing

As, at the time, botany was regarded as a legitimate female pursuit, which permitted easier access to scientific circles, quite a lot of women were engaged in collecting plants, preparing herbaria and making botanical

27. Anonymous, 'Photogenic Drawing', in: *The Magazine of Science and School of Arts*, 4 May 1839, 34–35, 34.

28. Ann B. Shteir, *Cultivating Women, Cultivating Science. Flora's Daughters and Botany in England, 1760 to 1860*, Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press 1996.

29. Larry Schaaf, *Sun Gardens. Victorian Photograms by Anna Atkins*, New York: Aperture 1985; Carol Armstrong, *Scenes in a Library. Reading the Photograph in the Book, 1843-1875*, Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press 1998.

Figure 12
Cecilia Glaisher, *Bree's fern*,
salted paper print mounted on cardboard,
c. 1854-56, 59 x 38 cm, intended for a
publication entitled „The British Ferns
Represented in a Series of Photographs from
Nature by Mrs. Glaisher from Specimens
Selected by Mr. Newman“.
Linnean Society.

Figure 13
Anonymous, *Botanical specimen (primrose)*,
albumen silver print, 20,8 x 13,8 cm.
National Gallery of Art Washington.

well-known photographers such as Cecilia Glaisher (fig. 12) and anonymous photographers (fig. 13) who made cameraless photographs around 1850/60. Either as scientific illustrations in the case of Glaisher, who attempted to publish her photographs of ferns in collaboration with the publisher Edward Newman, or as a collectible album created by an anonymous British photographer with objects including whole plants, feathers, insects etc.³⁰ Figure 13 shows a page with an illustration of a plant from an album now held in the National Gallery of Art Washington; it consists of individual parts reassembled to form a single plant of the primrose type. This composite picture refers to its ancestors in scientific illustration but, at the same time, also demonstrates an aesthetic approach as it does not hide its constructedness.

What I have tried to demonstrate is the intermingling of botany and cameraless photography resulting in the feminization of photography without a camera and its subsequent marginalization and invisibility in the history of photography. Although photogenic drawings could reveal invisible or hardly visible details of the plant structure such as venation or hair, drawings and engravings remained the general illustration method in botany. Emphasizing the automatic production method and the accurateness achieved through the direct contact between the object and photosensitive surface, photogenic drawings of botanical specimens need to be analyzed in closer connection with methods like nature printing where they will be seen to have a different genealogy than camera photography.

30. On Glaisher's photographs, see Caroline Marten, *Photographed from Nature by Mrs. Glaisher. The Fern Photographs by Cecilia Louisa Glaisher*, M.A. thesis, London Institute, 2002; The anonymous print comes from an album with 51 albumen silver print photographs. De-accessioned from the

Gloucester Public Library in England, it was sold as lot 20 at Sotheby's New York, October 8, 1997 and acquired jointly by Simon Lowinsky and Dan Solomon, who then split it.